

Illustrated Technical Paper - Reinforcement Learning Agent Design and Optimization with Bandwidth Allocation Model

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Abstract

This **ILLUSTRATED TECHNICAL PAPER** presents the slides and related discussion describing the contents of the paper "Reinforcement Learning Agent Design and Optimization with Bandwidth Allocation Model".

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The **ILLUSTRATED TECHNICAL PAPER** format is intended to facilitate the reader's perception of the paper contents by complementing, enriching, and subsidizing the technical paper content and slides with complementary text, and additional and/or focused bibliographic references.

Index Terms

Reinforcement Learning, Agent Design, Agent Optimization, Bandwidth Allocation Model, RL Task Offloading.

1 PAPER ABSTRACT

Reinforcement learning (RL) is currently used in various real-life applications. RL-based solutions have the potential to generically address problems, including the ones that are difficult to solve with heuristics and meta-heuristics and, in addition, the set of problems and issues where some intelligent or cognitive approach is required. However, reinforcement learning agents require a not straightforward design and have important design issues. RL agent design issues include the target problem modeling, state-space explosion, the training process, and agent efficiency. Research currently addresses these issues aiming to foster RL dissemination. A BAM model, in summary, allocates and shares resources with users. There are three basic BAM models and several hybrids that differ in how they allocate and share resources among users. This paper addresses the issue of an RL agent design and efficiency. The RL agent's objective is to allocate and share resources among users. The paper investigates how a BAM model can contribute to the RL agent design and efficiency. The AllocTC-Sharing (ATCS) model is analytically described and simulated to evaluate how it mimics the RL agent operation and how the ATCS can offload computational tasks from the RL agent. The essential argument researched is whether algorithms integrated with the RL agent design and operation have the potential to facilitate agent design and optimize its execution. The ATCS analytical model and simulation presented demonstrate that a BAM model offloads agent tasks and assists the agent's design and optimization.

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2 PAPER SLIDES

CSCI 2022
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Reinforcement Learning Agent Design and Optimization with Bandwidth Allocation Model

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Fig. 1.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

This article presents a strategy to offload computing tasks from a reinforcement learning agent using bandwidth allocation models (BAMs) [1].

The results suggest that to embed a BAM in a reinforcement learning agent design offloads some of the RL agent computational tasks, reduces the state-space of the agent, reduces the training process involved, and facilitates the agent design process [2].

-- > **Paper download:**

- The full paper is available at:

- * arXiv: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.12987>
- * ZENODO: <https://zenodo.org/record/7352192>
- * Research Gate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365686363_Reinforcement_Learning_Agent_Design_and_Optimization_with_Bandwidth_Allocation_Model

- ◆ Machine Learning (ML) trends
- ◆ ML Agent Design Issues
- ◆ BAM – What is it?
- ◆ Reinforcement Learning Task Offloading with BAM
- ◆ Considerations

Fig. 2.

Machine Learning Extensive Adoption Markets, Verticals and Trends

◆ Machine learning is being extensively adopted:

- 5G, 5G&B
- IoT and Future IoT
- Network slicing
- Vertical markets: V2X communications, medical applications, smart cities, and other
- Manufacturing: industrial IoT, machine vision, and other

Fig. 3.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"Reinforcement learning [3] is being extensively adopted for the solution and optimization of problems for real-life applications like 5G and beyond (5G&B), the internet of things (IoT), internet of vehicles (IoV), and network slicing [4] [5] [6] [7]. "

Machine Learning (ML) Issues

- ◆ ML agent dissemination in various areas
- ◆ Agent modeling and design approaches are necessary

→ ML agents with framework-supported development, structured test modeling, and efficient design approaches are current research trend

→ Need to facilitate and optimize ML agent design

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Fig. 4.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"The fostering of machine learning use in various areas depends, at least in part, on having agent modeling and design approaches or methods that make ML agents competitive concerning heuristics and meta-heuristics. In effect, it is expected that ML agents with formal, framework-supported, or speedy-like approaches could not only solve the unsolved problem using heuristics but also address the current problems that require intelligence or knowledge acquisition. "

"The design of machine learning agents is a fundamental issue currently addressed by research. As such, the design of machine learning agents needs frameworks, methods, or approaches to facilitate and optimize agent design. "

ML Agent Research

- ◆ Multi-agent RL - distributed agents
- ◆ Federated Learning (FL) - knowledge sharing among agents
- ◆ ML algorithm adopted (SARSA, Q-learning, Deep-Learning, ...)
- ◆ Agent modeling
- ◆ Training

Fig. 5.

- **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"Reinforcement learning agents are being developed for various application areas and the issues and problems related to these developments are mentioned in the literature and are the focus of attention [8] [9]."

"Machine learning agents in general are adopting new development and deployment approaches like distributing agents (multi-agent RL) [10] [11] and sharing knowledge among agents (federated learning) [12] [13]. The pushing of machine learning agents' design into new development strategies is, to some extent, motivated by the need to enforce efficiency."

"The agent design and optimization approach proposed in this paper is aligned with the strategy of using auxiliary algorithms, methods, or software to reduce the working state-space of the agent [14] [15]."

Bandwidth Allocation Model (BAM)

What is it?

- ◆ The bandwidth allocation models (BAM) allocate and share resources among users considering their class and priority
- ◆ Resources types: link bandwidth, EON slots, and other
- ◆ There are three basic BAMs:
 - ◆ Maximum Allocation Model (MAM);
 - ◆ Russian Dolls Model (RDM); and
 - ◆ AllocTCSharing (ATCS) model.
- ◆ Distinct models have different sharing strategies

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Fig. 8.

-- > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:

"The bandwidth allocation models basically allocate and share resources among users considering their priority [1]. There are three basic BAM models and several hybrids that basically differ in how they allocate and share resources among users."

"The three basic bandwidth allocation models that are considered in this discussion are:

- The Maximum Allocation Model (MAM) [18];
- The Russian Dolls Model (RDM) [19]; and
- The AllocTCSharing (ATCS) model [20]."

"All BAM models group resources in resource classes with priorities and each of the BAM mentioned above has resource allocation and sharing characteristics as follows [21]:

- In the MAM model, resources are grouped into isolated classes that never share their resources with other resource classes;
- In the RDM model, resources belonging to high-priority classes can be shared with lower-priority resource classes, and
- In the AllocTCSharing (ATCS) model, resources are shared among all resource classes regardless of their priority."

Bandwidth Allocation Model (BAM)

How do BAMs work?

- ◆ BAM group resources in resource classes
- ◆ The model allocates the resources to users grouped into classes
- ◆ Distinct models have different resource-sharing strategies among classes

→ ATCS model

Fig. 9.

— > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"The bandwidth allocation model parameters used to model the target problem and to manage BAM operation are as follows:

- Class resource constraint (R_{Ct_y}); and
- Class priorities (P_{Cl_j})."

"The class resource constraint is the number or amount of resources available to the class. Users request resources from classes."

"Although the application of BAM models has focused initially on sharing the resource bandwidth (link bandwidth sharing problem), it is worth highlighting that BAM resources may be generalized to allocate and share various discrete units used by computational systems like slots for elastic optical networks (EON) [22] and slice resource management [23], among others."

RL Agent Optimization with the ATCS BAM

- ◆ RL agent objective:
 - ◆ To allocate resources (bandwidth, EON slots, and others)
 - ◆ The same type of resource allocated and shared by the BAM models
- ◆ Optimization strategy:
 - ◆ ATCS model mimics RL agent operation for resource allocation (allocates resources on behalf of the RL agent); and
 - ◆ RL agent acts only by managing the ATCS model when resources become not allocatable.

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Fig. 10.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"The issue addressed in this paper is whether the ATCS model contributes to the design and operational efficiency of an RL agent whose objective is to allocate resources among users."

"We first argue that the ATCS model mimics an RL agent operation with similar allocating and sharing resources objectives. Consequently, the RL agent state-space is reduced since the BAM model does nearly all resource and sharing allocations until resources are exhausted. BAM operation, as such, facilitates the agent design and contributes to the optimization of its operation."

RL Agent Operation Dynamics – Use Case

- ◆ The RL agent operation is as follows:
 - ◆ A user requests resources (1)
 - ◆ ATCS BAM processes the request and finds out that there are no resources to allocate considering all sharing possibilities between resources classes (all resources available) (2)
 - ◆ ATCS call the RL agent to decide what to do (3)
 - ◆ RL agent decides if the model can or not be reconfigured by reallocating the resources between the resource classes (4):
 - ◆ Redistribution of resources is an intelligent action that uses knowledge acquired from user's profile requesting resources
 - ◆ Decision is based on administrator management objectives and technical requirements for the set of resource classes and users
 - ◆ Decision is to reconfigure and allocate or reject user request (do not reconfigure) (5)

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Fig. 11.

-- > PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:

"In the Figure 11 setup, all resource-allocating computation is offloaded from the RL agent, and the agent acts on behalf of the ATCS model exclusively to manage its configuration. It is worth mentioning that the ATCS model management is a high-level task that requires knowledge acquisition and operation expertise in alignment with the purpose of an RL agent."

"As such, the RL agent is invoked to manage the ATCS configuration parameters in a resource-exhausted condition. The RL agent is called because the ATCS model has no possibility whatsoever to allocate resources to users anymore when this condition is reached. "

RL Agent Optimization with the ATCS BAM

- ◆ RL agent with ATCS:
 - ◆ ATCS mimics RL agent computation
 - ◆ ATCS BAM offloads RL agent computation
 - ◆ RL agent state-space is reduced:
 - ◆ The BAM model does nearly all resource and sharing allocations until resources are exhausted
 - ◆ RL agent is invoked to manage the ATCS configuration parameters in a resource-exhausted condition

- ◆ There is a computational tradeoff between agent invocation and ATCS algorithm execution

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Fig. 12.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"The RL agent allocating resources task offload inherently reduces the state-space model for the agent. That is so because it is invoked only to reconfigure ATCS parameters, and the agent no longer executes all computation and state analysis concerning user resource requests. The same reasoning applies to the agent modeling and training phases. "

Final Considerations

- ◆ Reinforcement learning agents require advancements in terms of their design and efficiency
- ◆ RL agent task offloading is achieved by the ATCS model executing most of the computation required for allocating and sharing resources
 - ◆ RL agent acting only as a manager (intelligent and high-level decisions)
- ◆ RL agent with ATCS BAM:
 - ◆ Offloads RL agent computation;
 - ◆ Reduces the state-space of the agent;
 - ◆ Reduces the training process involved; and
 - ◆ Facilitates the agent design process.

Fig. 13.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

"The analytical model and the use case simulation presented demonstrate that an ATCS software offloads part of the computational tasks of a reinforcement learning agent aiming to allocate and share prioritized resources for users."

"The RL agent task offloading is achieved by the ATCS model executing most of the allocation and sharing of resources. This approach results in the RL agent acting as a manager, adjusting the ATCS configuration parameters when resources are exhausted and need an intelligent management decision."

"The proposed approach facilitates the agent design process, reduces the state-space of the agent, and, consequently, the training process involved."

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Fig. 14.

Questions and Discussion

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Fig. 15.

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